

Right to Internet: A Fundamental Right?

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Abstract:

The 'Internet' has been in existence since the 1960s, its current use throughout the world across different age groups and incorporation into virtually every aspect of modern human life, has been unprecedented. According to the International Telecommunication Union, the total number of Internet users worldwide is now over 2 billion. Active users of Face-book, an online social networking platform, grew from 150 million to 600 million between 2009 and 2011. It is believed that the Internet is one of the most powerful instruments of the 21st century for increasing transparency in the conduct of the powerful, access to information, and for facilitating active citizen participation in building democratic societies. Indeed, the recent wave of demonstrations in countries across the world has shown the key role that the Internet can play in mobilizing the population to call for justice, equality, accountability and better respect for human rights. As such, facilitating access to the Internet for all individuals, with as little restriction to online content as possible, should be a priority for all States. The influence and effects of 'Internet' on society, system and human communities through-out the world is accepted by all the ruling governments even by the international authorities regulating the rights and duties of human being and of the state. Hence it should be adopted, regulated and effectively monitored by various machineries of countries vide domestic laws of the nation. Our Constitution 1950, cyber security laws and Information Technology Act, 2000 and Indian Judiciary do ensure, protects and regulate the right to internet in India.

Introduction:

The 'Internet' has been in existence since the 1960s, its current use throughout the world across different age groups and incorporation into virtually every aspect of modern human life, has been unprecedented. According to the International Telecommunication Union, the total number of Internet users worldwide is now over 2 billion. Active users of Face-book, an online social networking platform, grew from 150 million to 600 million between 2009 and 2011. It is believed that the Internet is one of the most powerful instruments of the 21st century for increasing transparency in the conduct of the powerful, access to information, and for facilitating active citizen participation in building democratic societies. Indeed, the recent wave of demonstrations in countries across the world has shown the key role that the Internet can play in mobilizing the population to call for justice, equality, accountability and better respect for human rights. As such, facilitating access to the Internet for all individuals, with as little restriction to online content as possible, should be a priority for all States¹.

In this background, we can say that the access to the Internet has two dimensions i.e.

1. Access to online content, without any restrictions except in a few limited cases

permitted under International Human Rights Laws and Security Laws.

2. The availability of the necessary infrastructure and information communication technologies, such as cables, modems, computers and software, to access the Internet in the first place.

Rationale of the study:

The internet provides us with facts and data, as well as information and knowledge that contribute for the overall personal, social, and economic development in almost all the countries. But, the effective regulation of actions, functioning and restrictions in respect of various aspects of internet is the need of today. Hence, basic information and details about various aspects of 'internet' as right needs to be spread out.

Objective of the study:

1. To understand the role of internet in present scenario.
2. To find out the status of 'internet' under concerned statutes.

Hypothesis:

1. The 'internet' is not a matter of 'right'.
2. 'Internet' is only a mode of communication which is not adopted by many people.

Methodology:

Doctrinal research methodology is used. It is supported by secondary sources of

information, like articles, judgments, reports, commentaries, textbooks, etc.

The 10 Internet Rights & Principles²:

'The Internet' offers unparalleled opportunities for the realisation of Human Rights. Internet plays an increasingly important role in our everyday lives. It is therefore essential that all actions, both public and private, respect and protect Human Rights also on the Internet. Steps must also be taken to ensure that the Internet operates and evolves in ways that fulfil human rights to the greatest extent possible. In this context to ensure a rights-based internet environment, the 10 Rights and Principles are required such as -

1. **Universality and Equality:** All humans are born free and equal in dignity and rights, which must be respected, protected and fulfilled in the online environment.
2. **Rights and Social Justice:** The Internet is a space for the promotion, protection and fulfilment of Human Rights and the advancement of social justice. Everyone has the duty to respect the Human Rights of all others in the online environment.
3. **Accessibility:** Everyone has an equal right to access and use a secure and open Internet.
4. **Expression and Association:** Everyone has the right to seek, receive, and impart information freely on the Internet without censorship or other interference except legally imposed reasonable restraints to maintain a proper balance of rights and duties. Everyone also has the right to associate freely through and on the Internet, for social, political, cultural or other purposes.
5. **Privacy and Data Protection:** Everyone has the right to privacy online. This includes freedom from surveillance, the right to use encryption and the right to online secrecy. Everyone also has the right to data protection, including control over personal data collection, retention, processing, disposal and disclosure.
6. **Life, Liberty and Security:** The rights to life, liberty, and security must be respected, protected and fulfilled online. These rights must not be infringed upon, or used to infringe other rights, in the online environment.
7. **Diversity:** Cultural and linguistic diversity on the Internet must be promoted and technical and policy

innovation should be encouraged to facilitate plurality of expression.

8. **Network equality:** Everyone shall have universal and open access to the Internet's content, free from discriminatory prioritisation, filtering or traffic control on commercial, political or other grounds.
9. **Standards and Regulation:** The Internet's architecture, communication systems, and document and data formats shall be based on open standards that ensure complete interoperability, inclusion and equal opportunity for all.
10. **Governance:** Human rights and social justice must form the legal and normative foundations upon which the Internet operates and is governed. This shall happen in a transparent and multilateral manner, based on principles of openness, inclusive participation and accountability.

Constitutional protections to Right to Internet:

Constitution of India is a living document. Because it recognises and adopts various new rights expected by the society at large and which are required to protect other settled and recognised rights of individuals as well as of social rights. Recognition to right to internet is also such kind of right that is adopted by constitution vide judicial interpretation.

1. 'Right to Internet' protected under Article 19 of Constitution of India³:

Law and technology rarely mix like oil and water. There is a consistent criticism that the development of technology is not met by equivalent movement in the law. In this context, we need to note that the law should absorb the technological development and accordingly mould its rules so as to cater to the needs of society. Non recognition of technology within the sphere of law would be a huge harm to the system of the nation. Morning to night we are encapsulated within the cyberspace and our most basic activities are enabled by the use of internet, hence the importance of internet cannot be underestimated. The development of the jurisprudence in protecting the medium for expression is expanding time to time. In this context following points are notable -

- i. The Apex Court had declared that the freedom of print medium is covered under the freedom of speech and expression⁴.

- ii. It was held that the right of citizens to exhibit films on Doordarshan, subject to the terms and conditions to be imposed by the Doordarshan, is a part of the fundamental right of freedom of expression guaranteed under Article 19(1)(a), which can be curtailed only under circumstances set out under Article 19(2)⁵.
- iii.** The Apex Court expanded the protection to the use of airwaves in the case of Secretary, Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Government of India. It has recognized free speech as a fundamental right, and as technology has evolved, has also recognized the freedom of speech and expression over different media of expression. Expression through the internet has gained contemporary relevance and is one of the major means of information transmission. **Therefore, the freedom of speech and expression through the medium of internet is an integral part of Article 19(1)(a) and accordingly, any restriction on the same must be in accordance with Article 19(2) of the Constitution.**
- iv.** The internet is also a very important tool for trade and commerce. The globalization of the Indian economy and the rapid advances in information and technology have opened up vast business avenues and transformed India as a global IT hub. There is no doubt that there are certain trades which are completely dependent on the internet. Such a right of trade through internet also fosters consumerism and availability of choice. **Therefore, the freedom of trade and commerce through the medium of the internet is also constitutionally protected under Article 19(1)(g) and it is subject to the restrictions provided under Article 19(6)⁶.**
- 2. Internet as a part of right to education as well as right to privacy under Article 21:**
- i.** The Apex Court has held that⁷ in the light of Article 51(c) and 253 of the Constitution of India and the role of judiciary envisaged in the Beijing Statement, the International Conventions and norms are to be read into the fundamental rights guaranteed in the Constitution of India in the absence of enacted domestic law occupying the fields when there is no inconsistency between them. Going by the aforesaid dictum laid down in the said judgment, **the right to have access to Internet becomes the part of right to education as well as right to privacy under Article 21 of the Constitution of India.**
- ii.** In one more case it was held that women are having equal constitutional status and identity, while considering the case relating to pre-natal determination of gender, in order to assert that there cannot be any discrimination based on gender, the counter affidavit shows that restrictions are imposed in men's hostel also though the duration is different. However in paragraph 21 of that judgment, in which the interim order passed on 13.4.2017 was incorporated, the Apex Court made it clear that the freedom of expression included the right to be informed and right to know and feeling of protection of expansive connectivity. In that case, **the Apex Court took note of the instances on account of inappropriate exposure to the Internet and held that the respondents therein have a role to control it so as to see that there is no violation of the provisions contained in section 22 of Pre-Conception and Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Prohibition of Sex Selection) Act, 1994, relating to determination of gender⁸.** In this way the right to have access to Internet becomes the part of right to education as well as right to privacy under Article 21 of the Constitution of India.
- Restrictions on Right to Internet:**
This right is protected under Article 19⁹ and Article 21¹⁰ of the Constitution of India. Hence -
1. Restriction on the same must be in accordance with Article 19(2)¹¹ of the Constitution.
 2. Subject to the restrictions provided under Article 19(6)¹².
 3. The procedural mechanism contemplated for restrictions on the Internet, is twofold i.e. first is contractual, relating to the contract signed between Internet Service Providers and the Government, and the second is statutory, under the Information Technology Act, 2000, the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 and the Telegraph Act.

4. Prior to 2017, any measure restricting the internet generally or even shutting down the internet was passed under Section 144, Cr.P.C., a general provision granting wide powers to the Magistrates specified therein to pass orders in cases of apprehended danger. The High Court of Gujarat, vide order dated 15.09.2015, upheld the restriction imposed by the Magistrate under Section 144, Cr.P.C.¹³. However, the position has changed since 2017. Suspension Rules under Section 7 of the Telegraph Act. With the promulgation of the Suspension Rules, the States are using the aforesaid Rules to restrict telecom services including access to the internet.

International Aspect:

1. A Resolution 23/2 adopted by the Human Rights Council in the 23rd session of United Nation's General Assembly held on 24th June, 2013 on the role of freedom of opinion and expression in women's empowerment, in the light of the Convention on the elimination of all forms of communication against women and all previous resolutions of the commission on human rights and on the right to freedom of opinion and expression, including council resolution 20/8 of 5 July, 2012 on the promotion of protection and enjoyment of human rights on the Internet. The resolution also mandates for the signatory to facilitate equal participation in, access to and use of information and Communications technology, such as the Internet, applying a gender perspective and to encourage international cooperation aimed at development of media and information and communication facilities in all countries.

2. A Resolution has also been adopted by The United Nations General Assembly on 14 July, 2014 for the promotion, protection and enjoyment of human life on the Internet. It says that noting that the exercise human rights in particular the right to freedom of expression on the Internet is an issue of increasing interest and importance as the rapid pace of technological development enables individuals all over the world to use new information and communication technologies noting also the importance of building confidence and trust in the Internet, not least with regard to freedom

of expression, privacy and other human rights so that the potential of the Internet as interalia an enabler for development and innovation can be realised.

Common restraints of content on the internet:

- Arbitrary blocking or filtering of content.
- Criminalization of legitimate expression.
- Imposition of intermediary liability.
- Disconnecting users from Internet access, including on the basis of violations of intellectual property rights law.
- Cyber-attacks.
- Inadequate protection of the right to privacy and data protection.

Various aspects of rights to be ensured via internet:

1. Right to access to the internet: This right includes basic rights such as -
 - Quality of service.
 - Freedom of choice of system and software use.
 - Ensuring digital inclusion.
 - Net neutrality and net equality.
2. Right to non-discrimination in internet access, use & governance, it implies -
 - Equality of access.
 - Marginalized groups equality.
 - Gender equality.
3. Right to liberty & security on the internet i.e.
 - Protection against all forms of crime.
 - Security of the Internet.
4. Right to development through the internet via -
 - Poverty reduction and human development.
 - Environmental sustainability.
5. Freedom of expression & information on the internet i.e.
 - Freedom of online protest.
 - Freedom from censorship.
 - Right to information.
 - Freedom of the media.
 - Freedom from hate speech.
6. Freedom of religion & belief on the internet.
7. Freedom of online assembly & association on the Internet.
8. Right to privacy on the internet: This right needs to be ensured and enforced by -
 - National legislation on privacy.
 - Privacy policies and settings.
 - Standards of confidentiality and integrity of IT-systems.

- Protection of the virtual personality.
 - Right to anonymity and to use encryption.
 - Freedom from surveillance.
 - Freedom from defamation.
9. Right to digital data protection including crucial aspects like -
- Protection of personal data.
 - Obligations of data collectors.
 - Minimum standards on use of personal data.
 - Monitoring by independent data protection authorities.

Right to culture & access to knowledge on the internet implying rights of following nature -

- Right to participate in the cultural life of the community.
 - Diversity of languages and cultures.
 - Right to use one's own language.
 - Freedom from restrictions of access to knowledge by licensing and copyright.
 - Knowledge commons and the public domain.
 - Free/open source software and open standards.
10. Rights of children & the internet should also be considered and recognised. It must comprise -
- Right to benefit from the Internet.
 - Freedom from exploitation and child abuse imagery.
 - Right to have views heard.
 - Best interests of the child.
11. Right to work and the internet i.e.
- Respect for workers' rights.
 - Internet at the workplace.
 - Work on and through the Internet.
12. Right to online participation in public affairs by ensuring right to equal access to electronic services and right to participate in electronic government.
13. Rights to consumer protection on the internet.
14. Rights to health and social services on the internet.

Suggestions:

1. The statutory provisions dealing with the rights and duties about the individuals, dealers or other organisations should be spread out amongst the common people.
2. The effective implementation of the existing laws dealing with the internet

aspects should be ensured by the concerned machineries.

3. Every individuals using the internet for any purpose either as a mode of entertainment or platform of online trade and commerce should not misuse the same, should be used with good intention without bad motive and by following the given rules and regulations.
4. The internet service providers should follow the rules and regulations as given under the concerned laws and policies.

Conclusion:

The influence and effects of 'Internet' on society, system and human communities through-out the world is accepted by all the ruling governments even by the international authorities regulating the rights and duties of human being and of the state. Hence it should be adopted, regulated and effectively monitored by various machineries of countries vide domestic laws of the nation. Our Constitution 1950, cyber security laws and Information Technology Act, 2000 and Indian Judiciary do ensure, protect and regulate the right to internet in India.

Endnotes:

1. International Telecommunication Union, StatShot No.5, January 2011 Available from: <http://www.itu.int/net/pressoffice/stats/2011/01/index.aspx>.
2. <http://internetrightsandprinciples.org/site/campaign>
3. Secretary, Ministry of Information & Broadcasting Government of India v. Cricket Association of Bengal, (1995) 2 SCC 161; Shreya Singhal v. Union of India, (2015) 5 SCC 1
4. Indian Express v. Union of India, (1985) 1 SCC 641
5. Odyssey Communications Pvt. Ltd. v. Lokvidayan Sanghatana, (1988) 3 SCC 410
6. Anuradha Bhasin vs Union Of India on 10 January, 2020
7. Vishaka & Ors. v. State of Rajasthan & Ors. [AIR 1997 SC 3011 : (1997) 6 SCC 241]
8. Sabu Mathew George vs Union of India and others: (2018) 3 SCC 229
9. Protection of certain rights regarding freedom (a) to freedom of speech and expression; (b) to assemble peaceably and without arms; (c) to form

- associations or unions [or co-operative societies]; (d) to move freely throughout the territory of India; (e) to reside and settle in any part of the territory of India; (g) to practise any profession, or to carry on any occupation, trade or business.
10. Protection of life and personal liberty.— No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.
 11. The State may enact any law to imposes reasonable restrictions on the exercise of the right in the interests of [the sovereignty and integrity of India,] the security of the State, friendly relations with foreign States, public order, decency or morality, or in relation to contempt of court, defamation or incitement to an offence.
 12. State can enact any law relating to (i) the professional or technical qualifications necessary for practising any profession or carrying on any occupation, trade or business, or (ii) the carrying on by the State, or by a corporation owned or controlled by the State, of any trade, business, industry or service, whether to the exclusion, complete or partial, of citizens or otherwise].
 13. Gaurav Sureshbhai Vyas v. State of Gujarat, in Writ Petition (PIL) No. 191 of 2015

Other Reference:

1. Report of the Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of the right to freedom of opinion and expression, Frank La Rue: Submitted at Human Rights Council Seventeenth Session Agenda item 3Promotion and protection of all human rights, civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, including the right to development.
2. Internet Rights & Principles Coalition: © August 2014 – 4th Edition Internet Rights and Principles Dynamic Coalition UN Internet Governance Forum. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial-Share Alike 3.0 Unported License: Compiled and edited by Marianne Franklin, with Robert Bodle and Dixie Hawtin Design by Zeena Feldman
3. <http://indiankanoon.org/doc/82461587/>